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THE POLICE HEADQUARTERS TRAFFIC UNIT'S EFFECTIVENESS IN MANAGING DRIVING PERMITS

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Abstract: *This research was conducted to analyze the effectiveness of driving license (SIM) services at the Poles in Ternate City. The method is descriptive qualitative by conducting direct interviews with selected informants. The research found p procedure service in the Traffic Police. Ternate City is straightforward. It is because officers who carry out their duties know the standard of service they run. It And the existing operational standards at the Stapes Poles Ternate have been maximal, what meant is the maximum here is that the service here is to the existing operational standards in the regulations at the Traffic Police Office of the Ternate Police.*

Keywords: *Driving license; effectiveness; procedures; regulations; services.*

INTRODUCTION

Service is one of the essential tasks that cannot be ignored by local governments. Because the service component stagnates, it is almost sure that all sectors will have an impact on congestion; therefore there needs to be good planning and even need to formulate service standards for the community following the authority given by the central government in local government. A service is also an act of serving or providing services that are carried out to meet public needs and must be to public interests and satisfaction.

The effectiveness of service in an administration, administrators, has to listen a lot rather than inform, serve rather than control. It means realizing organizational effectiveness in achieving the goal required public service. It shows that service is essential and foremost in serving the public government as a service provider and the public as a service recipient. The demand for service effectiveness is essential to implement following the dimensions of service that are simple, clear and definite, open, efficient, economical and fair, as a manifestation of services implemented by government agencies such as the police. Based on the observations of researchers, the length of time and infrastructure are inadequate so that many choose to make SIMs instantly. The cost that needs to be incurred by people who use instant SIM services is IDR 300,000, - 500,000, - even though the actual cost of making a new SIM C is IDR 100,000, SIM A is new IDR 150,000, while for the extension of SIM C IDR 75,000, SIM A IDR 80,000. It is because the procedures and services of officers are considered by the community to be still not effective and efficient.

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This situation also causes the community to choose to make SIM through brokers/collectives/people in the police, because these methods are faster and more practical, even when viewed from the point of view of the cost of making a SIM, there is no significant difference between using a broker/collective/people in the police by taking care of them. This situation makes people prefer to use non-official channels which are faster and more practical.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research is qualitative research to get an overview of the effectiveness of SIM services at the Ternate Police Traffic Police Office. This study also used a descriptive approach; research is qualitative descriptive aims to describe the nature of the state while running time of the study and examine the causes of a particular symptom (Sevilla et al., 1993). Furthermore, according to Meleong (2008), a qualitative descriptive study is a research procedure that produced descriptive data in the form of words from people and observed behavior, which is to observe things or problems that occur and describe following the focus of the research problem. Meanwhile, according to Nazir (2003), the method Descriptive research with a qualitative approach is a method in researching the status of human groups, an object, a condition, a system of thought, or a class of events in the present facts and relationships a the next phenomenon investigated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The effectiveness of driving license (SIM) services at the Traffic Police of Ternate city

Effectiveness is the main element in achieving the goals or objectives determined by an organization. Effectiveness is the relationship between output and objectives, the more significant the contribution of output to the achievement of goals, the more influential the organization, program, or activity is (Mahmudi, 2005). Effectiveness comes from the word practical, which means the occurrence of an effect or the desired effect in an action. In the Big Indonesian Dictionary, the word effective means that it can produce results; it starts to take effect; there is an effect/affect/effect. Effectiveness can also interpret as a measure of success in achieving goals.

Furthermore, according to Kurniawan (2005), effectiveness is as follows: Effectiveness is the ability to carry out tasks, functions (program activity operations or missions) rather than an organization or the like where there is no pressure or tension between its implementations. According to Herizal et al. (2020), Public service accountability is one of the essential issues in scientific studies and practice in the field of public administration. Accountability is needed by public organizations to be the basis for providing explanations to all parties (stakeholders), both internal and external, with interest in evaluating or evaluating the actions and performance of public organizations.

Community service can be categorized as useful if the community has easy service with short, fast, precise, and satisfying procedures (De Jong & Niemantsverdriet, 1990; Janse et al., 1983). The finding from Traffic

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Police of Ternate City Police, the number of vehicles in Ternate City in 2017; 2 wheels is 193,551, wheels six as many as 7,371, and wheels four as many as 12. 591. From the data above to perform the service effectively. In this case, the police have given the authority to serve the community. Ternate City Police Traffic Control Unit in the field of controlling the service of a Two-wheeled Driving License (SIM C) which is implemented adequately is a reference or assessment of Polri agencies, especially Satlantas. The number of applicants for a two-wheeled driving license (SIM C) in Ternate City is enormous, of course, this brings many problems in its manufacture (Benoit et al., 2001; Wiberg, 2006). Problems that arise to be minimized by various rules, standard operating procedures, the competence of serving officers and appropriate policies that do not harm the service or those served so that it hoped that professional service could be. The following is the number of SIM applicants in Ternate City in the last five three years:

The number of applicants or users of SIM services at the Ternate City Police Traffic Unit must be balanced with an increase in service effectiveness because the community will demand better services from public organizations. So the thing that must be remembered is that service to society is a demand that cannot be ignored, society is the most critical part of the existence and continuity of an organization. According to Wance (2018), public services in Ternate City must be continuously improved, one of which is a city that has good public service, and accountability can be measured and tested. so that the Ternate City Government makes a licensing policy to serve all the needs of the community and performs a supervisory function on social and political conditions.

The time factor in SIM services at the traffic police of Ternate city

The work effectiveness of the organization depends on the work effectiveness of the people who work in it. Several criteria can be used to measure the work effectiveness of organizations that provide services (Siagian, 1987). Service According to Kotler (2001), is every action/activity or appearance/benefit offered by each party to another party which is intangible and does not result in ownership (Santosa, 2008). According to Mulyadi (2016), service providing services needs of people or communities who have an interest in the organization following the basic rules and procedures that have been combined). Furthermore, Boediono (2003), states that service is a process of assisting others in specific ways that require sensitivity and interpersonal relationships to create satisfaction and success.

Furthermore, according to Sinambela (2006), service is the key to success in various business or service activities. Its role will be more prominent and determine when service activities in the community are competitive to seize the subscription market, likewise in the government sector, the role of public services is held by the government, it has not been able to meet the expectations of all parties so that a management Ibrahim, A. H., Husain, T., Handji, S. B., & Suhu, B. L. (2020). The effectiveness of driving license services in police system is needed for the delivery of public services. Every human being needs service, even in the extreme, it can be said that service cannot be separated from human life (Hasyim, 2017). Whereas the results of Wance (2018), show that aspects of organizational characteristics, namely the exposure to organizational characteristics of PT ASDP Ferry Bastiong's public transportation services

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in Ternate, strongly support the process of achieving organizational goals in providing services and open accountability.

The punctuality here is the service according to the specified time. Where is the procedure that is easy to understand, and is straightforward, so that the community is directed towards proper implementation? The Ternate Police Service in terms of making a SIM has carried out its function in the service provided with timeliness following the stipulated regulations. The time factor is a critical factor in assessing public service. The following is the opinion of the SIM applicant regarding the timeliness given by the Ternate City Police Traffic Police SIM Affairs Office, among others, they already feel that the completion time is as promised by the authorities. Among other things, as was felt by one Salero resident who was taking care of SIM C, Astuti La Ode Garu (23 years): "It didn't take long, the service procedure was also easy. I came here and was greeted and directed to fill out a form for registration. My accidental came at 08.00 sirs, so no one was queuing up yet, so hurry up, sir, sir. It's half past 10 huh.... It took almost 2 hours for my driver's license to be finished". (Interview 12 May 2018).

Easy service procedures and under applicable regulations are a commitment to carrying out work professionalism and increasing and maintaining community satisfaction in making SIM (Battmann & Klumb, 1993; Diaz, 2002; Dananjaya & Sedana, 2020). The existence of procedures and requirements that are easy and simple is considered to be a very efficient in-service time. Services with the right time are services that can be completed within a predetermined time or do not stall for time in serving the SIM applicant community. The timeliness of the Ternate City Police Traffic Unit officers is critical because if the process of serving the community takes a long time, it will result in congestion or long queues.

Accuracy factors in SIM Services at the traffic police of Ternate city

The accuracy factor can be used as a measure to assess the level of work effectiveness of the organization that provides services. The accuracy factor here is the accuracy factor of the service provider to the customer. Customers will tend to give the service provider a not too high value, if there are many errors in the service process, even though it is given in a short time. Service will be fast and precise if the officer carefully looks, checks the applicant's form, and the applicant's examination results. This is done well; it will be used as a measure to assess the effectiveness of services. Based on the results of interviews with Briptu Agus F Sudarsono, SH (BA MIN and BA MAT) said that: "We are always careful about every incoming form that is registered for processing in conducting the exam. We are thorough and call on everyone to take the theory test and practice tests. Since we are here with limited equipment so we summon them for the test based on the names they registered first".

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be said that Ternate Police SatIntas officers have been professional and careful in serving various circles of society; this is evidenced by the accuracy of officers in serving SIM applicants in large numbers every day. This makes the SIM management services at the Traffic Police of the City of Ternate equally do not see the lower and upper classes of society, because all of this is done to create justice in the service process at the Ternate City Police. In rampant public

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complaints about the effectiveness of public services provided by the Traffic Police of Ternate City Police. Whether it is the time of service and the accuracy of service officers, to the convoluted service process, the Ternate City Police Traffic Unit officers strive to improve the effectiveness of public services. The form of efforts of the Traffic Police is to provide services by applicable procedures or regulations.

CONCLUSION

The service time factor at the Ternate City Police Traffic Unit has been going well, and this is indicated by the standard time that has been felt by the SIM applicant, the Ternate City Police Traffic Service in terms of making SIM C has carried out its function in the service provided with timeliness following the regulations set. This supports the achievement of good service and the success of the service that the community wants as well. The attitude/responsiveness of the Ternate Police Traffic Unit in responding to community complaints in solving problems is excellent. Furthermore, the Ternate Police Traffic Unit has carried out the complaint service process appropriately, to provide services following existing operational standards; officers are trying to understand what people want to take care of a SIM. One of the efforts made by Ternate Police Traffic Unit officers to provide good service so that no mistakes occur and no community feels disadvantaged.

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